

Church of the Holy Saviour in Chora

also known as “Kariye Mosque”, “Kariye Camii (Turkish)”, “Kari Cami-i Şerifi (Ottoman)”

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Entry tags: Constantinople, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Greek, Islam, Christian, Language, Turkic, Religious Place, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi

A church was purportedly first constructed on this site in the 4th century, and was rebuilt under the reign of the Byzantine emperor Justinian (r. 527-565). The earliest surviving archaeological evidence dates from the sixth century (Oates p. 226). After being damaged during the Latin period following the Fourth Crusade (1204), the church was repaired under the Byzantine emperor Andronikos II (1282-1328). The church's mosaics are from this period; several were commissioned between 1315 and 1321 by Theodore Metochites. Grand Vizier Hadim Ali Pasha, serving under the Ottoman emperor Bayezid II, converted the church into a mosque (Kariye Camii) in 1511, 58 years after the conquest of Constantinople. The mosaics were covered by plaster. The structure was designated as a museum in 1945. Between 1947 and 1948, the mosaics were restored, the building was conserved, and excavations were undertaken by the Byzantine Institute of America. The building was reconverted into a mosque in 2020.

Date Range: 300 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Church of the Holy Saviour in Chora

Region tags: Turkey

Church of the Holy Saviour in Chora, located in present-day Istanbul.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Underwood, Paul A. *The Kariye Djami 3: The Frescoes/Plates 335-553*. New York: Bollingen Foundation, 1966.

– Source 1: Gülersoy, Çelik. *Kariye (Chora)*. Istanbul: İstanbul Kitaplığı, 1981.

– Source 1: Kiraç, Suna & İnan. *Kariye: From Theodore Metochites to Thomas Whittemore: One Monument, Two Monumental Personalities*. Pera Müzesi, 2007.

– Source 1: Underwood, Paul A. *The Kariye Djami 2: The Mosaics/Plates 1-334*. New York: Bollingen Foundation, 1966.

– Source 1: Ousterhout, Robert G. *The architecture of the Kariye Camii in Istanbul*. Dumbarton Oaks, 1987.

– Source 1: Ousterhout, Robert. *The Art of the Kariye Camii*. London: Scala Publishers Ltd, 2002.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.choramuseum.com/>

– Source 1 Description: The official website of the Chora Museum, which includes articles written by academics about the history of the site.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Reference: Oates, David. "A Summary Report on the Excavations of the Byzantine Institute in the Kariye Camii". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 14 (1960): 223-31.

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1957-1958

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Excavations of the Byzantine Institute in the Kariye Camii

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
 - No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Originally (in the fourth century), the church at this site was located outside the city walls of Constantinople; by the sixth century, after the city had expanded, it was located within the city walls.

- ↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Notes: At the time of its original structure, the church was located outside of the city walls of Constantinople.

- ↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
 - Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Square

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Between the 4th and 14th centuries, this church was associated with a monastery.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The church was damaged during the Latin period (1204-1261), following the Fourth Crusade and sack of Constantinople.

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Other [specify]: Neglect

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

↳ In modernity
– Renaissance

Notes: After the church's conversion to a mosque in 1511, a mihrab was added, and mosaics were covered with plaster.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: God (Trinity)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Notes: Christ is considered fully divine.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Notes: According to the Life of St. Theodore, St. Theodore chose this location to build a monastery; however, this tale may be apocryphal.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: There was formerly a monastery associated with the church.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds primary importance among the structures.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 70

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 742.5

Notes: See Gülersoy, p. 7.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 17.3

Notes: Ousterhout, *The Architecture of the Kariye Camii in Istanbul*, figs. 14-20

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 742.5

Notes: Max Crandale, "Chora Church, Kariye Museum (Kariye Müzesi)," Chora Museum website.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 17.3

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Rare marble slabs were imported.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Glass is used for decoration (mosaics)

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals including horses and peacocks are depicted in the mosaics.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The marble slabs offer abstract decoration

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

Notes: Generally, the writing in the church (including within the mosaics) is informative, rather than decorative.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: The priest and deacons, but not the laity, could enter the sanctuary, which was separated from the nave by the iconostasis (icon screen).

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: There are frescoes present in the pareclision.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

Notes: Some mosaics feature written inscriptions, also made from mosaic tesserae.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: N/A.

↳ Other type of decoration:
– Yes [specify]: Decorative, matched marble slabs

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: A fresco in the Pareclesion depicts the gates of hell.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Four arcosolia (arched recesses) inside the church contained tombs.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Tombs within arcosolia

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No, but the Byzantine emperor was considered to be divinely appointed.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: The Byzantine emperor was considered to be divinely appointed.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: omnipotent

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Through answered prayer

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Through a comparative approach, Christ might be considered to be mixed human and divine nature; however, within the Byzantine empire, the relationship of Christ's human and divine natures was a central topic of debate.

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Christ is considered to be physically present in the Eucharist.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Icons are venerated, rather than statues.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 50-200

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Annually

Notes: Each major holiday occurs once per year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Wine is consumed as part of a religious ritual (communion).

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Eucharist is considered to be the blood and body of Christ.

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: The Eucharist is considered to be the blood and body of Christ.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Reconstruction

Notes: Major renovations occurred under Byzantine emperor Andronikos II (1282-1328).

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

- ↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
 - No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

- No

Are festivals present:

- Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Annually

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: 50-200

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes

Notes: Yes, but feasting for holidays likely took place at other locations.

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The church was associated with a monastery from the 4th through 14th centuries.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of the Holy Saviour in Chora, Oates, David. "A Summary Report on the Excavations of the Byzantine Institute in the Kariye Camii". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 14 (1960): 223–31.

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Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Oates, David. "A Summary Report on the Excavations of the Byzantine Institute in the Kariye Camii". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 14 (1960): 223–31.

